

Cytological Diagnosis of Pilomatrixoma-A Diagnostic DilemmaUpasana Mukherjee¹, Manisha Mahata², Madhumita Paul³, Rajashree Pradhan⁴,
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Abstract:

Pilomatrixoma is a benign neoplasm which originates from the hair matrix. Fine-needle aspiration cytology has been delineated as an important preoperative diagnostic test. Pilomatrixoma cytologically usually due to predominance of one component over another results in diagnostic dilemma. We report this case to highlight the difficulties faced by a pathologist to rule out the differential diagnosis and diagnose a case of PMX cytologically.

Keywords: Pilomatrixoma, cytology, Fine needle aspiration cytology.

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Introduction

Pilomatrixoma (PMX) also popularly known as calcifying epithelioma of Malherbe is a benign neoplasm which originates from the hair matrix. The most common location of the tumour is the head and neck region. [1] It usually occurs in the first two decades of life with a female preponderance. [2] It accounts for 20% of all pilar tumours. The patient usually presents with a slow growing dermal or subcutaneous nodule and it is very difficult to diagnose it clinically. [3]

Fine-needle aspiration cytology (FNAC) has been delineated as an important preoperative diagnostic test, though on cytology PMX is difficult to diagnose often resulting in fallacious diagnosis. [1] Usually, PMX has been falsely diagnosed cytologically as an epidermal inclusion cyst (EIC), giant cell tumour, squamous cell carcinoma or malignant adnexal tumour. Hence cytological diagnosis of PMX is sometimes difficult and often misdiagnosed. We report this case to highlight the difficulties faced by a pathologist to rule out the differential diagnosis and diagnose a case of PMX cytologically.

Case Report:

A 70 year old male presented to the surgery department with history of slow growing ulcerated lesion in the right zygomatic region for past 2 years associated with pus discharge. The patient was sent to the department of pathology for fine needle aspiration cytology (FNAC).

On examination the lesion measured 1.5x1 cm². On aspiration; a cheesy granular material was obtained. The slides were prepared following which the slides were stained with Leishman Giemsa and Papanicolaou stain (Pap).

Cytosmears were highly cellular comprising of basaloid looking cell (Figure 1), ghost cell, anucleate squames (Figure 1), foreign body giant cells (Figure 2), admixed with neutrophils (Figure 2). Few clusters of cells showed mild atypia. Final impression was given as infected pilomatrixoma with a note that due to presence of plenty of basaloid looking cells along with atypical cells, biopsy is suggested to rule out the possibility of basaloid Squamous cell carcinoma (SCC).

Figure 1: Showing clusters of basaloid cells and anucleate squames (PAP,100X)

Figure 2: Showing giant cells in a background of neutrophils (PAP,100X)

Discussion

Pilomatrixoma (calcifying epithelioma of Malherbe) is a benign skin appendageal neoplasm with differentiation towards hair follicle matrix cells. Head-neck region being the most common affected region followed by upper limbs, chest and the lower extremities. [4] Cytologically PMX is diagnosed usually by the presence of basaloid cells, calcium deposits, naked nuclei, shadow (“ghost”) cells, giant cells and inflammatory background but in 40% cases characteristic cytological findings of PMX are absent and the rate of correct identification of PMX by FNAC is 44%. [4] PMX has attracted attention in the cytological literature as one of the commonest cause of false positive diagnosis. Large numbers of tightly clustered and some single basaloid cells with scanty cytoplasm and medium sized, hyperchromatic, mildly irregular nuclei with small nucleoli may dominate the smears. These cells may look like those of basal

cell carcinoma, basaloid carcinoma or small cell anaplastic carcinoma. Mitotic figures and apoptotic bodies may be found, as well as moderate nuclear pleomorphism and atypical cells arranged in a whorled fashion may be seen and hence has to be differentiated from squamous cell carcinoma. Dirty background may be misinterpreted as tumour necrosis. Basal cell carcinoma, squamous cell carcinoma, small cell carcinoma and skin appendage tumour can be considered as differential diagnosis where the smears are predominantly composed of basaloid cells and when ghost cells or foreign body giant cells predominate, the cytologic differential diagnosis include epidermal inclusion cysts or giant cell lesions. [4]

There is a possibility of making a false positive diagnosis if clustered basaloid cells dominate the smears and the characteristic ghost cells, background calcification and giant cells are scant and overlooked. [5] Clinical findings, age, size and

history are important clues which should be correlated to arrive at a correct diagnosis.

Conclusion

This case report focuses on the importance of mindful screening of FNAC smears and creates awareness about the lesions that can mimic Pilomatrixoma cytologically usually due to predominance of one component over other results in diagnostic dilemma. Also, pilomatrixoma should be considered in lesion involving the head and neck.

Cytopathologists play a vital role in the preliminary diagnosis and should keep in mind the arbitrariness of the cellular composition seen in Pilomatrixoma to avoid misdiagnosis.

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Consent: Written informed consent was taken from the patient.

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